

Effects of Internet Use on Academic Achievement and Behavioural Adjustment Among Adolescents in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study aimed at the effects of internet use on academic achievement and behavioural adjustment among adolescents in Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku, Rivers State. Three research questions were formulated to guide the study. A descriptive survey design was adopted in this study. The major research instrument used for the collection of data was a structured questionnaire titled "Internet use and academic achievement questionnaire (IUAAQ)" which is made up of twenty-four (24) test-items. These were constructed using the four (4) point likert rating. The instrument for the study was drafted and arranged by the researchers, after which it was taken two (2) experts in computer science department and Educational Psychology department for face and content validity. The instrument was administered to the respondents and was required to respond to the questionnaire on the spot. The major statistical tool used in the analysis of data collected was mean score (\bar{x}). The study concludes that there is positive effect on the usage of internet by students (Adolescent) on their academic achievement and behavioural adjustment of adolescents. Based on the findings and conclusion, the study recommends that lecturers should do more in inculcating the habit of using the internet to students by giving them assignments that will compel them to use it for academic purposes and that orientation training programme should be organized by tertiary institutions at regular intervals so that the maximum users can improve their excellence or proficiency on the use of the internet for academic purpose while addiction to the internet toward their academic achievement.

Key words: *Internet, Academic Achievement, Behaviour Adjustment and Adolescents*

Introduction

The internet has become an essential component of people's everyday life throughout the world. This ranges from its support in improving the way people seek information, conduct research, perform

business transactions and communicate with others and various other features (Chou, 2011). According to Agil and Ahmad (2011), the internet is the transport vehicle for the information stored in files or documents in a computer. It carries together various information and services, such as electronic mail, online chat, file transfer, the interlinked web pages and other documents of the world wide web. In today world, the internet plays a vital role in the teaching, research and learning process in academic institutions. With a growing demand for internet access on campuses, universities have contributed to this growth as they perceive the internet to be a valuable source of information for students and a tool to enhance their productivity (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). It is a powerful and efficient tool for searching, retrieving and disseminating information, with a significant impact on students and scholars worldwide. This has made adolescents to be heavy users of the internet compared to the general public (Juold & Kennedy, 2010). Some adolescents prefer digital communication over more traditional ways such as face to face interaction and telephone calls (Madden & Rainie, 2003), particularly because these are more convenient, less expensive, and faster to use than traditional technologies (Bryant Sanders, Jackson & Smallwood, 2006). Email and text messaging allow for rapid, asynchronous communication with others while constant messaging allows for synchronizing communication among many people at once. Adolescents use instant messaging more frequently than adults among online population in the world.

Young (2011) shows in her study that the internet has become a cause of concern among the general population because of its addictive-like applications and services. The internet just like any addictive substance can therefore have a negative influence on its adolescent extensive users. Due to a growing demand of internet access on campuses, students are regarded as heavy users of the internet compared to the general public (Jones, 2012).

A general consensus exists amongst researchers that the adoption of the internet and its technologies does have a negative influence on students' academic achievement and behavioural adjustment such as psychological problems including social isolation, depression, loneliness and difficulties with time management as a result of excessive internet use (Young & Rodgers, 2018). Excessive use of the internet may bring an internet addiction disorder which includes problems with daily routines school performance and family relationships (Rickert, 2011). Other challenges associated with excessive usage of the internet includes lowered concentration, lack of sleep, poor school attendance and performance, vision problems and a wide range of behavioural problems (Block, 2018; Choi, 2017). In addition, Young adolescents are at high risk of being approached by online predators since they are relatively new to online activities, actively seeking attention, isolated easily, tricked by adults and confused their sexual identity (Ybarra & Mitchell, 2005). Although they become more interested in sexuality (Ponton & Judice, 2008), they are innocent about the sexual issues that get youth into trouble online (Wolak, Finkelhor, Mitchell & Ybarra, 2008). Adolescents who do not have open communication about their internet use with their parents are more likely to be involved in risky internet behaviours, such as having a face to face meeting with a stranger who they encountered online (Liau, Khoo & Ang, 2005).

Gender is the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between masculinity and femininity (Haiger, in Onuogbo, 2012). Depending on the context, the term may refer to biological sex (i.e. the state of being male, female or intersex), sex based social (including gender roles and other social roles) or gender identify. To Okeke (2013) cited in Ordua (2020), gender refers to the socially and culturally constructed characteristics and roles which are ascribed to males and females in a society.

Gender is not a major factor that determine internet usage on academic achievement among adolescent, rather females use the internet more than their males counterparts, thus could be possible

because, the female counterparts is always on social network for the purpose of looking for social partners such as boyfriends etc (Kim, 2011).

This study is therefore on effects of internet use on academic achievement and behavioural adjustment among adolescents in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku.

Statement of the Problem

It has been found out that most of the internet users nowadays are the adolescents which most of who are students in both secondary and tertiary institutions. These adolescents make use of the internet for various reasons and purposes which includes seeking for information, communication with friends via chatting and instant messaging, buying and selling of products accessing movies or songs, sending e-mail, gathering information from news, playing online games, making business contacts, social networking with people, academic research and sourcing for study materials. However, time spent in activities where “surfing the net” occurs could substitute away from time allowed to reading, studying, completing homework. Thus may hurt academic achievement and leads to behavioural adjustment among adolescent. So, the study assessed the effectiveness of the internet use services and its effects on adolescent’s academic achievement and behavioural adjustment.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to find out the effects of the use of internet on academic achievement and behavioural adjustment among adolescents.

Specifically, the researchers sought to determine:

- i. The effects of internet use on academic achievement among adolescents.
- ii. The effects of internet use on behavioural adjustment among adolescent.
- iii. The differences in gender usage of internet on academic achievement among adolescent.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What are the effects of internet use on academic achievement among adolescent?
- ii. What are the effects of internet use on behavioural adjustment among adolescent?
- iii. What are the differences in gender usage of internet on academic achievement among adolescent?

Method

The research design adopted for the study is descriptive survey design. According to Nworgu (2015), a descriptive survey design describes a condition or phenomenon as it exists naturally without manipulation. The area of study was Omoku, the population of this study was 460 adolescents from Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study adopted a purposeful sampling technique. A sample size of 214 adolescents from the population of study was selected for the study. The researchers used a questionnaire titled “internet use and academic achievement questionnaire” (IUAAQ) to elicit information from the respondents. The instruments were made up of two sections A & B. Section A consists of questions that elicits demographic information while section B consists of 24 items instruments. The response was categorized into 4 points rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) respectively.

The researchers employed direct delivery method in administration of the instruments to the research subject. This implies that the researchers administered the instruments personally to the respondents and the two hundred and fourteen (214) were found to have been correctly filled and fit for use in further analysis. That data were collated to obtain mean scores. The data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean to answer the research questions. Mean scores of 2.5 was the benchmark. Hence,

any item with mean score 2.5 and above was considered positive and accepted, while items with mean scores of 2.49 below were considered negative and rejected.

Results

Research Question One: What are the effects of internet use on academic achievement among adolescents in Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku.

Table 1: Response from students on the effects of internet use on academic achievement among adolescents.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Remarks
1.	Internet boost students positively in their academic work	68	114	12	17	3.07	0.84	Accepted
2.	Internet provides access to numerous resource materials	49	135	15	15	3.02	0.76	Accepted
3.	Internet makes learning easy	60	124	14	16	3.07	0.80	Accepted
4.	Internet reduces stress in learning in academics	75	104	21	14	3.12	0.84	Accepted
5.	It makes connectivity and communications with teachers easy	71	100	23	20	3.04	0.90	Accepted
6.	It helps in self study	73	77	39	25	2.93	0.99	Accepted
7.	Students use internet in online discussions	103	75	18	18	3.23	0.92	Accepted
8.	It helps students to complete assignments and presentations	80	87	21	26	3.03	0.98	Accepted
	Grand Mean					3.06		

Source: Field survey (2021)

Table 1 above indicates that from the responses of students (adolescent) that all the items 1 – 8 were accepted. This means that the effect of internet usage on student academic achievement is positive with an average mean of 3.06.

Research Question 2: What are the effects of internet use on behavioural adjustment among adolescent?

Table 2: Response from students on the effects of internet use on behavioural adjustment among adolescent.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
9.	Internet usage influences students psychosocial behaviour	75	105	17	17	3.11	0.86	Accepted
10.	Internet usage leads to students self-esteem	35	149	15	15	2.95	0.72	Accepted
11.	Internet learning leads to stress	49	124	20	21	2.99	0.85	Accepted
12.	Internet usage by students leads to motivation	54	118	21	21	2.95	0.86	Accepted
13.	Internet usage by students leads to social integration	55	105	34	20	2.91	0.85	Accepted
14.	Internet usage by students leads to poor learning attitude	53	90	43	28	2.79	0.96	Accepted
15.	Internet usage by students can lead to depression	90	79	22	23	3.10	0.97	Accepted
16.	Internet usage by students can lead to reduction in study skills	80	87	21	26	3.03	0.98	Accepted
	Grand mean					2.98		

Source: Field survey (2021)

Table 2 above indicates that from the mean response of the students (adolescent) that all items 9-16 were accepted. This means that there is effect of internet use on the behavioral adjustment among students (adolescent). This result shows an average mean of 2.98 which is above the acceptable mean of 2.50

Research Question 3

What are the differences in gender usage of internet on academic achievement among adolescent of F.C.E.(T), Omoku?

Table 3: Response from students on the effects of gender on internet usage on academic achievement among adolescent of F.C.E.(T), Omoku.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Remarks
17	Males use internet more than females in academic work.	18	85	71	40	2.38	0.88	Reject
18	Females use internet more than males in academic work	17	89	56	52	2.33	0.93	Reject
19	Internet usage is gender sensitive	14	57	68	75	2.05	0.93	Reject
20	Males complete their tasks more easily than females when using the internet	20	19	101	74	1.93	0.90	Reject
21	Females complete their tasks more easily than males when using the internet	29	12	106	67	2.01	0.95	Reject
22.	Males use the internet more frequently than females in their academic work	6	8	72	128	1.50	0.70	Reject
23	Females use the internet more frequently than males in their academic work	61	31	79	43	2.51	1.10	Accept
24	Adolescent use of internet results in some anti-social behaviours	61	106	21	26	2.94	0.93	Accept
	Grand mean					2.21		

Source: Field Survey (2021)

Table 3 above indicates the mean responses of students (adolescents) for items 17-22 which indicates a mean lower than the acceptable mean of 2.50 which is rejected while items 23 and 24 have mean above 2.50 which shows acceptance. Therefore since the grand mean of 2.21 is below the acceptable mean, it is rejected which means there is no effect of gender on internet usage on academic achievement among adolescent of F C E (T) Omoku

Discussion of Findings

The result obtained from Research Question one revealed that students' use of internet for their academic studies is positive and it leads to high achievement in their academic endeavours. For instance, studies conducted by Ogungbem et al (2016) shows that the appropriate use of internet among undergraduates in Nigeria. Also the finding of Sahin, Balta and Ercas (2010) supports the findings, indicating that students use of internet as a very important tool in their research works and course of learning for a high academic achievement.

The computed outcome of the research question two was found to be statistical positive. This evidently shows that there is effect of internet on adolescents behavioural adjustment. The use of the internet leads to psychosocial behavior such as self-esteem, motivation, stress, social integration, poor learning habits and also reduction in learning skills. This is in line with the findings of Singh, Gupta and Garg (2013) that adolescents spent most of their time of non-focused activity such as facebook and other social networking activity resulting in loss of time on concentration on their academic work. This result in psycho-

social behaviour. Also the result is supported by the study of Bragdom and Dowler (2016) and that of (Krischne & Karpinsking (2019). The result obtained from research question three revealed that gender (sex) has no effect on academic achievement, rather that females use the internet more than their males counterparts, this could be possible because, the female counterparts is always on social network for the purpose of looking for social partners such as boyfriends etc. this finding it supported by the findings of Kim, 2007.

Conclusion

The study investigated the effect of internet on academic achievement and behavioural adjustment among adolescents in Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku. Internet has become an essential component of people's everyday life throughout the world ranging from it's support in improving the way people seek information, conduct research, perform business transactions and communicate with others and various other features, and studies have shown that adolescents exposed to internet are much more likely to experiences a positive impact in achieving academic excellence. The effects on the usage of internet by adolescents on their behavioural adjustment because of its addictive like applications and services. The internet is just like any addictive substances that have a negative influence on its adolescent extensive users and behavioural adjustment such as psychological problems. It was observed that females use the internet frequently than their males counterparts on academic work. The use of internet by adolescents results in some anti-social behaviours. The main purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of internet use on academic achievement and behavioural adjustment among adolescents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Lecturers should do more on inculcating the habit of using the internet to adolescents b giving them assignments that will compel them to use it for academic purpose.
2. Orientation training programmes should be organized by tertiary institutions at regular intervals so that the maximum users can improve their excellence or proficiency in the use of the internet for academic purposes.

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